

DEFECTS COCKPIT

98,7
MEAN OEEQ

TOP 3 DEFECTS

11,19%
Paper glued to the plate (press)

10,30%
Broken paper

9,53%
Broken paper (paper stations)

RECIPE MATRIX

OEEQ Evolution

